

US NGO Completes the Science Verification of the GNIRS XD Pipeline

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Fig. 1. Frames taken with the GNIRS cross-dispersed mode. Credit: Rachel Mason / Gemini Observatory.

Figure 1: Front page of the website with the updated documentation for XDGNIRS

The Gemini Near-IR Spectrograph (GNIRS) instrument was built 20 years ago in Tucson, Arizona, at NOAO (now part of NSF's NOIRLab). Capable of low-, medium-, and high-resolution spectroscopy, GNIRS was designed to observe the 0.8–5.4 μm wavelength regime. Once the instrument was completed in 2003, it was moved to the Gemini South Telescope on Cerro Pachón, part of the International Gemini Observatory, and made

available to the public during the 2004B semester. Four years later, GNIRS was damaged and moved to Gemini North on Mauna Kea for repairs. The restoration was completed in 2010, and GNIRS was mounted on its new home on Gemini North, where it has remained ever since.

Today, GNIRS is the second most subscribed instrument on Gemini North, accounting for nearly 20%

of its total yearly science exposure time. When requesting time for spectroscopy with GNIRS, users have been able to choose between two modes: single long-slit (sensitive to 1.0–5.4 μm) or cross-dispersed (0.8–2.5 μm). As of 2023, low- and high-resolution IFU capabilities have been added to the instrument. In addition to the impressive spectroscopic capabilities of GNIRS, it can also be used for imaging with a field of view of around 10 arc-

seconds, compatible with broad and narrow band filters.

GNIRS's most popular configuration, 32 mm XD (cross-disperser mode), has an unofficial semi-automatic data reduction pipeline (XDGNIIRS, built on Gemini IRAF tasks) that had not been verified to produce science-grade products. This pipeline can be used in addition to other current software (Gemini IRAF, IDL, and Python) used to reduce GNIRS data. The US National Gemini Office (US NGO) staff performed a science verification and modernization project on the XDGNIIRS pipeline between October 2022 and July 2023. The project involved testing the pipeline on various astronomical sources, updating the code's syntax to be compatible with Python 3.7.11, and ensuring that the code complies with the software installed in the latest version of the Gemini Virtual Machine.

The science verification began with reducing data for the brown dwarf WISE0410 and the galaxy NGC3031. After successfully processing the data for these two objects using XDGNIIRS, the US NGO staff partnered with the Brazilian NGO head, Alberto Ardila, who has abundant experience using the GNIRS instrument. A list of eight galaxies with published spectra and varying weather conditions was compiled, as denoted on the Gemini Observatory Archive. All eight example datasets were successfully processed through the new version of XDGNIIRS, and an inspection of the final results confirmed that all the

Figure 2: GNIRS usage over time. Data taken from the Gemini Observatory Archive.

emission/absorption lines identified in the published spectra were also present in the spectra generated by the new version of the pipeline. XDGNIIRS also handled data marked as “poor quality” without any issues. The reduced spectra closely resembled the published versions.

In addition to updating the pipeline's code, two new resources were created for the users: a GitLab repository and a Read the Docs version of the pipeline's updated user manual. The GitLab repository contains the pipeline's code and the 15 datasets used to test the pipeline, which includes the reduced data products so users have a template for comparison. The documentation contains all the information included in the original

manual and instructions for the new features that were added in this version, including an updated ability to query SIMBAD for a source's redshift. The documentation also includes a section that displays all the acceptable inputs that either allow the user to manually perform specific tasks or perform additional tasks that the pipeline does not perform by default, such as the 'shift_to_rest' command, which obtains the source's redshift from SIMBAD and shifts the reduced spectrum into the rest frame.

The updated version of XDGNIIRS is now available to all Gemini users and can be accessed through this GitLab repository. A more detailed project summary can be found on the US NGO website.